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1. Executive Summary

The Croatian Ministry Of The Sea, Transport And Infrastructure (MMPI) collected and pre-processed AIS data, sharing them with the GUTTA partnership for the sake of the project’s objectives.

2. Introduction

According to the AF The GUTTA project’s SO 2 is to facilitate the implementation of the MRV by interfacing between and private actors. However, this objective is partly obsolete due to the the delayed start of the IT-HR Programme. In fact, the MRV is already fully in place and EMSA has been publishing related data since June 30, 2019. [1]

Therefore, in the GUTTA Major Amendment (currently under preparation) it will be proposed that SO2 deals with assessment of MRV data and process already in place. Ferry trajectories recorded through the AIS system may help this task. Also, the tool for computation of least-CO2 ferry routes in the Adriatic pertaining to GUTTA SO1 and which preliminary results were documented in [2] might benefit from AIS data for the sake of validation (WP5). Therefore, the present deliverable is renamed and focussed on supporting this new activity.

For Croatia, the system analysing and processing AIS data is the SEG (SafeSeaNet Ecosystem Grafical User Interface). MMPI started in project RP4 the process of extracting AIS data via common Grafical User Interface from EMSA’s SafeSeaNet (SSN) server for providing them to the LP of the project. This report documents such activity.

Note: for shortcuts, please refer to GUTTA Glossary available at: <https://zenodo.org/record/3676344>

3. AIS

According to the IMO-SOLAS Convention, an Automated Identification System (AIS) must be operational on all ships of more than 300 GT operating on international voyages. The AIS system consists of an automatic transmitter-receiver device (“transponder¹”) installed onboard and base stations located on islands and mainland or satellite. It allows vessels mutual exchange of various types of identification data in determined geographical area and with base stations located in islands and mainland. The information transmitted by vessel is of three different types:

static information (such as: IMO number, call sign & name, type of ship, length and beam);

dynamic information (such as: ship’s position, time in UTC, heading, course, speed, navigational status);

voyage related information (such as: ship’s draught, type of hazardous cargo, destination and ETA, route plan);.

This report contains dynamic information data, collected via AIS for six Ro-Pax vessels (Table 1) that sailed in the Adriatic sea between Croatia and Italy in a selected period of one year.

More details about data provided by MMPI to the GUTTA LP is described in the Section 3.1

Table 1 Basic information about ships

	Vessel name	Operator	IMO number	MMSI
1	Aurelia	SNAV	7602120	209510000
2	GNV Azzurra	Grandi Navi Veloci	7826790	247237700
3	Dubrovnik	Jadrolinija	7615048	238143000
4	AF Francesca	Adria Ferries SpA	7602089	247312600
5	Marko Polo	Jadrolinija	7230599	238144000
6	Zadar	Jadrolinija	9021485	238201000

3.1 Information about the database

The database is in xlsx. form and contains AIS datasets with information about:

- geographical position of the ship displayed in [latitude, longitude] coordinates

¹ <https://www.imo.org/en/OurWork/Safety/Pages/AIS.aspx>

- time stamp in [yyyy-dd-mm; hh:mm:ss] format
- ship speed in [m/s]
- ship heading as an angular distance relative to north [° N]

All parameters mentioned above are provided at a minimum update frequency of minutes or hours, depending on the capabilities of transmitter device installed on ship. The period considered ranges from 14.12.2019 to 14.12.2020. In Table 2 a sample is provided.

Table 2 AIS dataset sample.

Timestamp	Latitude	Longitude	Heading	Speed (m/s)
2020-06-14 01:54:00	4108.25N	01652E	173	0
2020-06-14 02:00:01	4108.25N	01652E	222	0.051444
2020-06-17 10:00:28	4108.25N	01652.03E	131	0.205778
2020-06-17 10:12:30	4108.34N	01651.49E	121	1.646222
2020-06-17 10:24:40	4108.14N	01651.97E	92	0.874556
2020-06-17 23:27:31	4108.68N	01651.01E	311	4.990111
2020-06-17 23:39:40	4110.18N	01652.36E	88	6.019000
2020-06-17 23:45:50	4110.21N	01653.85E	88	5.453111
2020-06-18 00:52:19	4109.43N	01713.24E	86	6.842111
2020-06-18 00:58:19	4109.59N	01715.01E	83	6.996444
2020-06-18 02:17:41	4111.81N	01738.58E	86	6.996444
2020-06-18 02:23:50	4111.89N	01740.42E	87	7.047889
2020-06-18 04:37:20	4113.24N	01819.85E	86	6.893556
2020-06-18 04:43:21	4113.34N	01821.64E	86	6.790667
2020-06-18 06:32:30	4115.13N	01853.29E	87	6.739222
2020-06-18 06:50:41	4114.81N	01858.51E	86	6.790667
2020-06-18 06:56:49	4114.98N	01900.29E	82	6.842111
2020-06-18 08:21:50	4116.03N	01925.11E	86	6.636333
2020-06-18 08:34:01	4116.98N	01927.2E	19	3.704000
2020-06-18 08:38:10	4117.41N	01927.43E	21	3.395333
2020-06-18 08:41:52	4117.8N	01927.58E	358	3.395333
2020-06-18 08:46:12	4118.28N	01927.31E	342	3.858333
2020-06-18 08:46:36	4118.33N	01927.31E	354	3.652556
2020-06-18 09:04:20	4118.79N	01927.24E	148	0.051444
2020-06-18 22:19:27	4118.76N	01927.25E	157	0.257222
2020-06-18 22:31:47	4118.52N	01927.22E	172	2.829444
2020-06-18 22:49:47	4116.4N	01926.56E	255	4.064111
2020-06-18 23:01:56	4116.12N	01924.8E	264	4.630000
2020-06-18 23:07:58	4116.03N	01923.53E	266	5.401667

4. Conclusions

MMPI has started providing the GUTTA partnership with AIS data information. This activity will continue with 2021 data and will be useful for the validation part of the project (WP5).

References

[1] G. Mannarini, L. Carelli, and A. Salhi. EU-MRV: an analysis of 2018's Ro-Pax CO₂ data. In 21st IEEE International Conference on Mobile Data Management (MDM), pages 287–292. IEEE, 2020.

doi.org/10.1109/MDM48529.2020.00065

[2] G. Mannarini, L. Carelli, J. Orović, C. P. Martinkus, and G. Coppini. Towards Least-CO₂ Ferry Routes in the Adriatic Sea. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 9(2), 2021.

<https://www.mdpi.com/2077-1312/9/2/115>